

Technical Assistance and Productivity of Public School Teachers in Sulop District, Davao Del Sur

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Abstract. This study aimed to determine the extent of technical assistance as a determinant of the productivity of public-school teachers in Sulop District, Davao del Sur Division. The findings revealed that providing technical assistance regarding roles, benefits, and obstacles is extensive. However, the indicators and roles are very extensive. Aside from the obvious benefits to the mentee, a mentor also stands to learn from the experience. The indicators of roles in providing information about policies, procedures, and paperwork to teachers were rarely extensive. Teachers need to be guided and provided with clear instructions to succeed in their actions. Moreover, the productivity of teachers in terms of physical facilities, grants and aids, staff management, and learning environment was moderately extensive. Indicators such as grants aids and learning environments were oftentimes manifested. However, the indicators regarding physical facilities and staff management were less extensive. The result revealed a significant relationship between the provision of technical assistance and the productivity of teachers. Teachers need to be provided with the appropriate technical assistance necessary for effective facilitation of learning. Technical assistance in terms of obstacles significantly influences the productivity of teachers. Indeed, the presence of obstacles challenges the productivity of teachers in the teaching-learning process.

KEY WORDS

1. technical assistant 2. productivity 3. public school teacher

Date Received: May 25, 2024 — Date Reviewed: June 01, 2024 — Date Published: July 5, 2024

1. Introduction

In the ever-evolving landscape of education, the role of teachers has undergone a significant transformation on a global scale. Technical assistance is deemed necessary to ensure effective program implementation and, eventually, achievement of higher or better learning outcomes. With the integration of technology into classrooms, the concept of technical assistance for educators has emerged as a pivotal factor influencing their productivity and effectiveness. Technical assistance helps teachers navigate and use technology more effectively by providing them with the necessary training and support. This assistance includes professional development programs, access to educational software, and on-site technical assistance. As a result, effective technical assistance not only improves teachers' instructional capabilities but also frees up their time, allowing them to spend more time engaging with students and developing innovative teaching strategies. Furthermore, correlations between the teaching context and stress outcomes were shown to be indirect, underscoring the importance of job satisfaction and work-

load in determining teacher stress. The symbiotic relationship between teachers and technology has created opportunities for enhancing pedagogical approaches, instructional methods, and overall student learning outcomes. As teachers navigate the dynamic intersection of traditional teaching methods and digital advancements, the provision of robust technical assistance has become essential to harness the full potential of educational technologies. Technical assistance is instrumental in increasing the productivity of public school teachers by providing them with the necessary guidance, resources, and support to engage in research activities effectively. Through technical assistance, teachers receive help in designing and implementing research projects, ensuring that they employ appropriate methodologies and data collection techniques. This support extends to developing teachers' data analysis skills, enabling them to derive meaningful insights from their research findings. Moreover, technical assistance fosters a culture of professional growth by encouraging teachers to reflect on their practice and experiment with innovative teaching strategies. Technical assistance encompasses a range of support mechanisms aimed at aiding educators in effectively utilizing various technological tools and platforms. This assistance could include training sessions, troubleshooting guidance, curriculum integration strategies, and ongoing mentoring. The incorporation of technology into education not only requires teachers to adapt to new tools but also demands a fundamental shift in instructional paradigms. As such, the quality and accessibility of technical assistance can significantly impact a teacher's ability to leverage technology in ways that foster student engagement, personalized learning, and holistic skill development (Maier, 2022). Collaboration and peer learning are also facilitated, as teachers share their experiences and best practices with colleagues engaged in similar research endeavors. By promoting evidence-

based decision-making and cultivating a culture of inquiry within schools, technical assistance empowers teachers to continuously improve their instructional practices, ultimately leading to enhanced student learning outcomes. By examining existing literature and studies, we aim to elucidate the multifaceted benefits of tailored support for educators in their quest to harness the potential of educational technologies while addressing the associated impediments. In doing so, we underscore the significance of investing in comprehensive technical assistance programs that empower teachers to create vibrant, technology-enhanced learning ecosystems (Harust et al., 2022). Teachers, acting in the capacity of instructional leaders, look for ways to support and aid their colleagues in carrying out their duties and obligations in supporting students' learning through practical lesson plans of activities and suitable, sufficient, and current educational resources. The advancement of the teachers' professional growth depends on technical support from the instructors. Mentoring fosters in-depth reflection on a school's objectives, philosophy, and procedures. Therefore, a mentor teacher should promote discussion of all aspects of the current school environment and be bold enough to urge teachers to be open to varied viewpoints, values, and beliefs (Belibas et al., 2020). Strong basic education is the key to this State strategy, which is stated in the 1987 Philippine Constitution: "Establish, maintain and promote a comprehensive, adequate, and integrated system of education responsive to the requirements of the people, the country, and society-at-large." Therefore, teachers are crucial in ensuring that this policy is followed. The government recognized this and established mechanisms to "promote and improve the social and economic status of public-school teachers, their living and working conditions, their terms of employment and career prospects so that they may compare favorably with existing opportunities in other walks

of life, attract and retain more people in the teaching profession” (Magna Carta for Public School Teacher). Technology is perhaps the strongest factor shaping the educational landscape today. Many school districts are showing support for increased levels of technology in the classroom by providing hardware such as tablets and computers, enhancing internet connectivity, and implementing programs designed to improve computer literacy for both teachers and students. Although teachers generally appreciate the benefits of educational technologies, they often find smooth and effective integration of new educational technologies challenging. From the acquisition of new technology equipment to adaptation of curricula and teaching techniques to incorporate new educational tools, technology integration presents significant challenges to educators at each level of school sys-

tems (Hakim, 2020). The rapid changes in the mode of learning can increase or hinder the capabilities of teachers to perform well in their classes, creating a varied response in the productivity. Detalla (2024) stated that successfully initiating and implementing educational technology in a school’s program depends strongly on the teachers’ support and attitudes. It is believed that if teachers perceive technology programs as neither fulfilling their needs nor their students’ needs, it is likely that they will not integrate the technology into their teaching and learning. Considering the overall situation, the researcher is keen to delve into the technical support provided by teachers to evaluate their productivity while mentoring their mentees in the field and to provide answers to specific questions in schools in Davao del Sur Division.

2. Methodology

This chapter presented the methods used in the study, which consisted of the research design, research respondents, research instrument, data gathering procedure, and data analysis. This study aimed to determine teachers’ technical assistance and productivity in Sulop District, Davao del Sur Division.

2.1. Research Design—This study employed the descriptive-correlational method to determine the public relations and productivity of teachers in public school teachers in the Davao del Sur Division. According to Aggarwal and Ranganathan (2019), descriptive research was crucial in improving our lives. Surveys help create better policies, and cross-sectional studies help us understand problems that affect different populations. Descriptive research could advance knowledge and inform decision-making in the right context. The purpose of correlational research was to establish a relationship in making predictions. Relationship investigations typically study several variables related to a major and complex variable. This design involves determining information about

variables and individuals. A survey study was employed to measure the existing phenomenon. In this study, the researcher employed quantitative descriptive research using correlation analysis. Quantitative research, characterized by its emphasis on numerical data and statistical analysis, was deemed appropriate for this study.

2.2. Research Respondents—The study’s respondents were randomly selected teachers of Sulop District, Davao del Sur, Division, who had been in the service for three (3) years and were deemed permanent employees. The sample size was obtained using the fishbowl technique. In this technique, the researcher was randomly picked out from the fishbowl of all teachers in their respective schools. These employees were considered the respondents of the

study.

2.3. *Research Instrument*—The researcher utilized adapted questionnaires from the studies of Utami and Vioeza (2021), which were modified to suit the present study’s concept, place, situation, and ideas. The draft of the research instrument was submitted to the research adviser for comments, suggestions, and recommendations. The final copy of the research survey questionnaire was validated by the panel of experts for approval. The final revision incorporated all the corrections, comments, and suggestions the experts gave before distribution and administration. Some expert validators presented and evaluated the draft of the questionnaire. They were provided with a standard evaluation tool to rate, comment on, and suggest improvements and development of the questionnaire. The validation results, together with the draft of the research instrument, were submitted to the research adviser for comments and suggestions. The ambiguous items were deleted, and the weak items were strengthened and im-

proved. After correction and refinement, the research instrument was returned to the researcher for finalization. The pilot testing was conducted in Sulop District, Davao del Sur, and the respondents were not included in the research survey. The pilot testing was purposely conducted to establish the reliability and validity of the test instrument. The questionnaire was designed and modified to suit the needs of the respondents. Cronbach’s alpha 0.08 was calculated to determine the reliability and validity of the survey questionnaire after taking a score from each scale item and correlating it with the total score for each observation. The resulting correlations are then compared with the variance for all individual item scores. This study used adapted and modified questionnaires. The first set was designed to draw out information concerning the extent of technical assistance regarding roles, benefits, and obstacles. The five-point Likert scale was used in this study to describe the productivity of teachers:

Range of Mean, Descriptive Level, and Interpretation of Technical Assistance Observations

Range of Mean	Descriptive Level	Interpretation
4.20 - 5.00	Very Extensive	The technical assistance is always observed.
3.40 – 4.19	Extensive	The technical assistance is oftentimes observed.
2.60 – 3.39	Moderately Extensive	The technical assistance is sometimes observed.
1.80 – 2.59	Less Extensive	The technical assistance is seldom observed.
1.00 – 1.79	Not Extensive	The technical assistance is never observed.

The questionnaire used a 5-point Likert scale to determine the extent of technical assistance. The following interpretations of the data are found below.

The second set was designed to collect data on teacher productivity regarding physical fa-

cilities, grants/aids, staff management, and the learning environment in Sulop District, Davao del Sur Division. Because validation and comprehensive instrument content were necessary, the researchers sought a knowledgeable person for comments and suggestions.

2.4. *Data Gathering Procedure*—

Range of Mean, Descriptive Level, and Interpretation of Teacher Productivity

Range of Mean	Descriptive Level	Interpretation
4.20 - 5.00	Very Extensive	The productivity of teachers is always observed.
3.40 – 4.19	Extensive	The productivity of teachers is oftentimes observed.
2.60 – 3.39	Moderately Extensive	The productivity of teachers is sometimes observed.
1.80 – 2.59	Less Extensive	The productivity of teachers is seldom observed.
1.00 – 1.79	Not Extensive	The productivity of teachers is never observed.

The researcher followed the following procedures in this study. The necessary data were gathered through the following procedure: The researcher asked permission from the office of the Schools Division Superintendent of Davao del Sur Division to conduct an online survey of the teachers of Sulop District. Likewise, the granted letter of permission from the Schools Division Superintendent was brought to the school heads and supervisors of public schools in Sulop District for the arrangement of the conduct of the research study. On November 18, 2023, the graduate student received an endorsement letter from the Dean of the Graduate School for the division superintendent's

approval. On November 29, 2023, a permission letter for the Schools Division Superintendent, the School Heads, and the concerned gender and development coordinators was prepared for accessible data collection. Upon approval, the researcher personally administered the research, conducted the survey, and retrieved the data through an online platform on May 5, 2024. The survey questionnaire was sent to the respondents' email, and once answered, it was sent to the researcher's email. The school heads secured a copy of the letter presented to vouch that the researcher had honestly conducted and collected the data from the study participants online.

2.5. *Data Analysis*—The following statistical tools were used, and the null hypothesis was tested at a 0.05 significance level. The data were gathered, tallied, and treated using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences. Mean. The weighted arithmetic mean applies to options of different weights (Calmorin, 1998). This study used this statistical tool to measure the extent of technical assistance and school organizational innovation. Pearson's r. The person

product-moment of the correlation coefficient was a linear correlation to find the degree of the association of two sets of variables (Calmorin, 1998). This statistical tool was used in this study to determine the significant relationship between technical assistance and the productivity of teachers in the Davao del Sur Division. Regression Analysis. The regression analysis was used to determine the domains of technical assistance that significantly influence the productivity of teachers.

3. Results and Discussion

This chapter presents the discussions of the problems in this study. They are discussed thoroughly, analyzed, and interpreted under the following headings and sequence: technical assistance and school organizational innovation.

Summary of the Extent of Technical Assistance Table 1 presents the data on the summary of teachers' technical assistance. The overall mean of the data in this table is 3.89. The indicators are presented with the corresponding mean: roles (4.34), benefits (3.80), and obstacles (3.51). All the indicators have the mean descriptive equivalent of Extensive.

Table 1. Summary of Technical Assistance of Teachers

Indicators	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
Roles	4.34	Very Extensive
Benefits	3.80	Extensive
Obstacles	3.51	Extensive
Overall mean	3.89	Extensive

The Extensive mean rating in this study suggests that teachers' technical assistance is often-times manifested, which means that it addresses the professional needs of teachers' coaching ability in the classroom. The results depicted in Table 4 are supported by the idea of Handrianto et al. (2022). This study aims to discuss two important variables in teachers' role as educators in school institutions: benefits and obstacles. Benefits are believed to help teachers enhance their teaching quality and students' involvement. Obstacles refer to the challenges teachers encounter that, in turn, increase their productivity. Furthermore, Altonji et al. (2019) found that mentoring and professional development play an important role in shaping teachers' roles as educators. Mentoring programs offer invaluable support and guidance to both new and experienced teachers, promoting ongoing growth and improvement in teaching practices. Mentorship allows teachers to improve their pedagogical skills, improve classroom management techniques, and adapt instructional strategies to meet their students' diverse needs. Similarly, ongoing professional development opportuni-

ties allow educators to keep up with emerging trends, technologies, and educational best practices.

Summary of Productivity of Teachers Table 2 shows a summary of the teachers' productivity, which reveals that the overall mean is 3.35. The three indicators are presented with their corresponding mean ratings: Physical facilities, 4.00; Grant and aids, 4.0; Staff Management, 2.70; and Learning Environment, 2.69. Two of these indicators have the descriptive equivalent of extensive, while two of the indicators have the descriptive equivalent of less extensive. When considering the importance of physical facilities, grants and aids, staff management, and the learning environment, the overall mean of 3.35, or moderately extensive, indicates that these factors play an important role in shaping the educational experience. Adequate physical facilities, as well as access to grants and aids, help to facilitate effective teaching and learning by providing necessary resources and support. Furthermore, effective staff management ensures that educators possess critical skills such as communication, teamwork, and flexibility,

all of which are essential for creating a positive learning environment. Finally, creating an environment in which teachers are encouraged to share their knowledge and strategies, combined with genuine enthusiasm for education, improves the overall quality of teaching and learning in schools.

Table 2. Summary of Productivity of Teachers

Indicators	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
Physical Facilities	4.00	Extensive
Grants and Aids	4.00	Extensive
Staff Management	2.70	Less Extensive
Learning Environment	2.69	Less Extensive
Overall mean	3.35	Moderately Extensive

The findings are consistent with the study by Dirsa et al. (2022) that high-scoring physical facilities have a significant impact on teacher productivity. This is because the quality of physical facilities has a direct impact on the teaching environment, providing educators with the resources and infrastructure they need to perform their roles effectively. As essential components of education, well-equipped physical facilities help to improve teaching quality and character development in schools. Gregory et al. (2018) hypothesized that high-scoring grants or aids have a significant impact on teacher productivity by increasing efficiency and effectiveness in classroom duties and responsibilities. Teachers who receive adequate support in the form of grants and aids can gain access to resources and tools that will allow them to excel in classroom instruction. The assistance provided by these resources, combined with effective school leadership, contributes to teachers' success and productivity within the educational agency. Ngo et al. (2022) found that low-scoring staff management has a significant impact on teacher productivity, emphasizing the importance of dynamic and harmonious relationships within educational organizations. When staff management is ineffective, it can result in interpersonal conflicts, low morale, and inefficiencies in com-

munication and collaboration among teachers. As a result, such challenges reduce teachers' overall productivity and effectiveness in carrying out their roles in the educational setting. Furthermore, the study's findings support the assumption of Krishna et al. (2019) that a low-scoring learning environment has a significant impact on teacher productivity. When the learning environment lacks conducive factors such as adequate resources, support systems, and a positive culture, teachers' ability to engage students and deliver quality instruction suffers. As a result, such challenges lower teacher morale, motivation, and overall effectiveness, reducing their productivity in the classroom. The findings suggest that physical facilities, grants and aids, staff management, and the learning environment all have a significant impact on teacher productivity in educational settings. Adequate resources and support systems contribute to effective teaching and positive learning outcomes, whereas issues with staff management and the learning environment can undermine teacher morale and effectiveness. Addressing these factors is critical for increasing teacher productivity and educational success. Significant Relationship between the extent technical assistance and productivity of teachers

Shown in Table 3 are data about the signif-

icant relationship between teachers’ technical assistance and the productivity of teachers. Analyzing the data by Pearson Product –Moment Correlation Coefficient or Pearson r, the results

are: the computed r-value for technical assistance versus productivity of teachers is 0.62 which denotes an almost substantial relationship or definite relationship.

Table 3. The Significant Relationship between Technical Assistance and Productivity of Teachers

Variables		r-value	t-value	p-value	Remarks/Decision
Technical Assistance (x)	Productivity of Teachers (y)	0.62	4.41	0.013	Reject

Note: Significance when $p < 0.05$

While computing the significant difference of t-values, it is found as 4.41 with a probability value of 0.013, which is less than the 0.05 significance level. Hence, there is a significant relationship between technical assistance and the productivity of teachers. The greater the technical assistance, the greater the productivity of teachers; hence, a positive correlation occurs when an increase in two variables decreases at the same time. This mere example of linear correlation or straight-line relationships between two variables. A correlation can range between -1 (perfect negative relationship) and +1 (perfect positive relationship), with 0 indicating no straight-line relationship. Given the results, teachers’ technical assistance revealed relevance with the productivity of teachers. Technical assistance is instrumental in enhancing teacher productivity by providing training, resources, and support to improve teaching practices. By equipping educators with innovative instructional strategies, effective classroom management techniques, and up-to-date subject knowledge, technical assistance fosters an environment conducive to increased productivity in the classroom. Significant Influence of Technical Assistance on the productivity of

teachers. Table 4 depicts the regression coefficient analysis on the significant influence of technical assistance that significantly influences the productivity of public-school teachers in the Davao del Sur Division. All indicators of technical assistance provided, namely roles (0.343), benefits (0.151), and obstacles (0.014), indicate a statistically significant influence on teachers’ productivity. This gives empirical evidence to show that the indicators of technical assistance provided directly influence teachers’ productivity. Meanwhile, the R2 value of 0.384 suggests that technical assistance accounts for 38.4 of the variance in teachers’ productivity. This provides empirical evidence that variability in the extent of confidence can be accounted for and explained by the indicators enumerated under the extent of teachers’ productivity in the Davao del Sur Division. In addition, the F-value shows all the sums of squares, given regression being the model and Residual being the error. The F-value (115.460) and F-statistic are significant $p_i.001$, which tells that the model is significantly a better predictor of technical assistance in the school and the obstacles significantly influence the productivity of teachers.

Table 4. Regression Coefficient Analysis on Technical Assistance That Significantly Influences the Productivity of Teachers

Model	Unstandardized	Standard Error	Standardized	t	p	Decision
(Intercept)	3.356	0.056		60.083	<.001	
Roles	0.095	0.090	0.100	0.949	0.343	Accept Null
Benefits	0.131	0.092	0.157	1.444	0.151	Accept Null
Obstacles	0.213	0.092	0.256	2.461	0.014	*Reject Null
R ²	0.384					
F value	115.460					
p-value	<.001					

Thus, technical assistance enabled teachers' productivity. Technical assistance in terms of roles, benefits, and obstacles motivated teachers to do better in their craft. According to Cornelius et al. (2020), the similarity of teaching assignments between mentor and mentees is typically regarded as a necessary prerequisite for successful mentoring relationships. Yet, due to personnel shortages and specialized teaching assignments in special education, it is not always possible to match novice special educators with veteran special educators. Outcomes assessed included the intervention's impact on the mentors' special education knowledge, mentors' ability to identify needed components of special education lesson delivery, and novice teachers' improvements in instructional practice and results indicated a functional relationship between the intervention and mentor knowledge as well as the ability to identify components of specialized instruction. Most impor-

tantly, novice special educators improved their instructional practices after being mentored by those who received professional development and specialized coaching. Betlem et al. (2019) explored that governments worldwide have invested in teaching standards and performance benchmarks to improve teacher preparation and teacher quality that impacts student achievement. As a means of addressing these imperatives, the Australian government has recently encouraged formal partnerships between tertiary providers, schools, and education systems in delivering teacher education and professional development, for mentors. Sims et al. (2021) remarked that several influential reviews and two meta-reviews have converged on the position that teacher professional development (PD) is more effective when it is sustained, collaborative, subject-specific, draws on external expertise, has buy-in from teachers, and is practice-based.

4. Conclusions and Recommendations

This chapter discusses the research's focal points and the statistical analysis's results. It also presents the conclusions and recommendations based on the study's findings. This study aimed to determine the level of technical assistance as a determinant of the productivity of teachers in the Davao del Sur Division.

4.1. Findings—The finding reveals that teachers' technical assistance, in terms of roles, benefits, and obstacles, was oftentimes manifested. The result emphasizes that technical assistance activities are parallel to learners' learning goals. The teaching and learning process was properly prepared, including how it would be communicated to the learners. On the other hand, the dependent variable was teachers' productivity in terms of physical facilities, grants/aids, staff management, and learning environment. The indicators physical facilities and grants/aids garnered extensive, staff management indicates less extensive, and learning environment moderately extensive. There was a significant relationship between technical assistance and the productivity of teachers; an R^2 value of 0.384 suggests that the teacher's public relations account for 38.4 of the variance of the teacher's productivity. The F-value (115.460) and F-Statistics were significant $p < .001$, which tells that the model is significantly a better predictor of teachers' technical assistance in the school. Results indicated that there was sufficient evidence to reject the null hypothesis. Thus, there was a significant relationship between the two variables. The roles and benefits, with $p < 0.343$ and $p < 0.151$, mean that the probability value is less than the acceptance region with these indicators. The null hypothesis is accepted, and therefore, these domains of technical assistance do not significantly influence the productivity of teachers. While roles and benefits do not significantly influence the productivity of teachers, this may be another factor that affects their productivity.

4.2. Conclusions—Based on the overall findings of this research, the following conclusions were drawn: The findings revealed that technical assistance in terms of roles, benefits, and obstacles is extensive. This noted that teachers need mentors who are measurably aligned with the learning objectives that would provide mentees with opportunities for inter-

action. Similarly, the productivity of teachers in terms of physical facilities, grants/aids, staff management, and learning environment in Sulop District, Davao del Sur Division, was moderately extensive and thus oftentimes manifested. There was a significant relationship between the extent of technical assistance and the productivity of teachers in Sulop District, Davao del Sur Division. The more effective the technical assistance, the higher the productivity of teachers; hence, a positive correlation occurs when an increase in two variables decreases at the same time. Two indicators of technical assistance; roles, and benefits, are not significant in influencing the productivity of teachers in Sulop District, Davao del Sur Division.

4.3. Recommendations—With the presented conclusions of the study, the following were recommendations, to wit; Public School District Supervisors. The Public School District Supervisor in Sulop District may improve the monitoring of technical assistance aimed at increasing teacher productivity and, as a result, student academic achievement. By optimizing staff management and learning environment, they can ensure that support initiatives directly contribute to better learning outcomes. School Heads. This study may provide school heads with information to sustain innovative practices in intensifying the implementation of different technological assistance. They should provide more avenues for teachers to intensify their technical assistance to their profession such as better staff management, instructional materials, and physical infrastructures. Teachers. Teachers may benefit from this study by having access to targeted technical assistance aimed at increasing productivity. With comprehensive monitoring and support, they may be able to improve their teaching methods and effectively use resources, potentially leading to better educational outcomes for their students. Learners. This study may benefit learners because it focuses on improving academic achievement. By

ensuring that teachers receive the necessary support and resources, students may benefit from a more conducive learning environment, potentially leading to increased engagement, understanding, and overall academic performance. Future researchers. Future researchers may benefit from this study because it provides insights into effective strategies for supporting teachers and improving learning outcomes. The findings may provide valuable input for future educational research, potentially leading to the development of evidence-based practices and policies aimed at improving educational quality and equity.

5. References

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